

Development of cyclic regeneration catalytic systems for low temperature methane decomposition

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by

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Preface

The present work was developed at the Laboratory for Process Engineering, Environment, Biotechnology and Energy (LEPABE) and at the Associated Laboratory in Chemical Engineering (ALiCE) in the Chemical Engineering Department of the Faculty of Engineering of the University of Porto (FEUP), and at the Institute for Chemical Technology (ITQ), in the Polytechnic University of Valencia (UPV), between 2021 and 2024 under the FCT (Foundation for Science and Technology) grant 2020.10008.BD. The present work was supervised by Professor Adélio Mendes and Doctor Gonzalo Prieto.

This thesis presents six chapters: one introduction chapter; four chapters of scientific research, each scientific chapter corresponds to a research article (published or being published); and a final chapter with the general conclusions and perspectives of future work.

ABSTRACT

Hydrogen is a suitable primary vector for producing clean fuels for industrial, residential, and transport applications. Catalytic methane splitting consists of the low-temperature cracking of methane, producing only CO_x-free hydrogen and solid carbon. This process has the unique potential to make the swift transition to a fully decarbonized economy. Yet, low-temperature catalytic methane splitting systems are hindered due to fast catalyst deactivation caused by solid carbon that encapsulates the catalyst. Catalyst regeneration must be performed to reactivate the catalyst and achieve a long-term operational lifetime. This can be accomplished by cyclically refeeding a portion of the produced hydrogen back to the catalyst, which promotes the hydrogenation of carbon atoms at the interface between carbon deposits and catalytic metal nanoparticles. Interfacial hydrogenation breaks the bonds that connect carbon allotrope products to the catalyst, causing the former to detach and freeing the catalytic surface for further reaction.

This thesis is a comprehensive study of the regenerative effects of interfacial selective hydrogenation in Ni-based catalytic methane splitting systems. For these systems to be regenerable, the carbon produced during the reaction must be able to detach the catalyst surface. To allow this, the Ni catalyst was structured and applied as a monolayer to leave space for carbon to grow over and eventually detach and drop off the catalyst during regeneration. This monolayer was deposited in substrates, which dictated the macrostructure of the system – bulk Ni foils, α -Al₂O₃ slabs, and carbon fibers were used throughout to prepare the catalytic systems. Bulk and ceramic-supported Ni-based catalysts were tested. Bulk particulate Ni (unsupported Ni particles) displayed activity for the reaction, although stability was low – the catalyst deactivated rapidly. Bulk particulate Ni deactivation was reversible by applying cyclic interfacial hydrogenation. 22 cycles of methane splitting were performed at 550 °C and 1 bar and during ca. 5 h, although overall H₂ productivity was low – 0.20 g_{H₂}·g_{Ni}⁻¹ (0.60 g_C·g_{Ni}⁻¹). Supported nanoparticles of Ni were consistently shown to be the most active and stable catalysts among the studied Ni-based systems. Regardless, they still end up deactivating after some time. Interfacial hydrogenation was again demonstrated to revert deactivation. However, the carbon growth mechanism was seen to have a fundamental role in the degree of activity recovered. Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ catalyst displayed a mixture of tip- and base-growth mechanisms, which made regeneration gradually less effective. The catalyst became fully deactivated after 25 cycles – 32 g_{H₂}·g_{Ni}⁻¹ (95 g_C·g_{Ni}⁻¹) in ca. 100 h.

A new nanostructured supported catalyst was prepared to suppress the tip-growth mechanism. Mesoporous 5 μm round SiO₂ particles were used to support Ni particles. The Ni particles were partially confined inside the 20 nm pores of the support (narrow pore size

distribution). The partial confinement hinders the diffusion of carbon toward the metal-support interface. With this Ni/SiO₂ catalyst deposited in a carbon fiber substrate, full regenerability was achieved at 550 °C with high activity – ca. 1 g_{H₂}·g_{Ni}⁻¹·h⁻¹ average activity. This system was operated for 3000 h, displaying total activity recovery from cycle to cycle. A gradual second-order deactivation was observed, which led to slight activity loss after many hours on stream – ca. 4 x 10⁻⁴ g_{H₂}·g_{Ni}⁻¹·h⁻². This gradual second-order deactivation was reversible – when cyclic methane feed was replaced for inert gas (24 h feeding Ar or He), the second-order deactivation was fully reverted. The total production after 3000 h was ca. 1100 g_{H₂}·g_{Ni}⁻¹ (3300 g_C·g_{Ni}⁻¹). This catalyst was then operated at 750 °C. Operation at higher temperatures yielded higher activity and a softer deactivation rate within a given cycle, greatly increasing average activity. However, the tip-growth mechanism was no longer fully suppressed. Doping the catalyst with a molar fraction of 1 % Fe improved stability and allowed for full selectivity of the base-growth mechanism at 750 °C. The catalyst displayed a stable activity as a function of the time, and the cyclic interfacial hydrogenation is no longer needed to regenerate the catalyst, rather it is performed to periodically release carbon allotropes.